

PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF STRUCTURAL BEHAVIOR MONITORING USING SMART SENSORS

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ABSTRACT

Cracks in aging concrete structures reduce mechanical integrity and often require localized repair. However, assessing the effectiveness and long-term performance of such repairs remains a challenge, especially in inaccessible or load-critical zones. In this study, I propose a carbon nanotube (CNT)-reinforced epoxy composite combined with aggregates to form a self-sensing concrete system capable of monitoring local compressive stress in real time. The system leverages the piezoresistive properties of CNTs within a polymer matrix to detect mechanical loading. I explored the influence of CNT concentration on electrical conductivity, mechanical performance, and sensing repeatability. The composite with 0.25 wt% CNT content exhibited high electrical sensitivity, mechanical robustness, and reproducibility under cyclic loading. This research highlights the potential of CNT-epoxy concrete as a multifunctional repair material that offers both reinforcement and embedded sensing.

1 INTRODUCTION

The deterioration of concrete structures due to aging and environmental exposure remains a major challenge in civil infrastructure. Surface and internal cracks not only weaken structural capacity but also accelerate corrosion and degradation processes. Repair strategies are often employed to restore mechanical integrity; however, assessing the long-term performance of these repaired areas is difficult with conventional inspection methods. Visual inspections and acoustic techniques require human involvement and do not offer continuous or real-time assessment, which leads to uncertainty and delayed responses to potential failure.

To address this limitation, self-sensing repair materials have been proposed, aiming to integrate sensing capabilities directly into the repair matrix. Among the various approaches, cementitious composites with embedded conductive fillers such as steel fibers, graphite, or carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have been studied for their piezoresistive behavior. For example, Jung et al. [1] developed ultra-high-performance concrete (UHPC) with embedded CNTs for both electrical field curing and crack detection. The system showed piezoresistive response under loading, demonstrating potential for field casting and real-time sensing. However, like many cement-based systems, the approach faced limitations related to CNT dispersion quality and sensitivity, particularly in the pre-cracking regime.

While such cement-based approaches offer some advantages in durability and structural integration, their low elasticity and limited CNT dispersion efficiency often result in insufficient sensitivity and poor repeatability. Polymer-based matrices, particularly epoxy resin, have shown better potential in this regard. Epoxy's high viscosity allows for improved CNT dispersion when aided by techniques

such as ultrasonication and three-roll milling. Moreover, the superior adhesion, chemical resistance, and toughness of epoxy make it a common material for high-performance repairs. Jung and Jang [2] previously proposed a CNT–polyurethane composite “smart skin” for detecting cracks in concrete, confirming the feasibility of CNT/polymer systems for localized sensing applications.

Despite these advancements, CNT-polymer systems incorporating structural aggregates—capable of functioning not only as a sensing layer but also as a load-bearing repair material—have not been fully explored. Most existing studies either neglect aggregate inclusion or limit the application to thin coatings. However, for practical field use, it is essential that self-sensing repair materials possess both structural robustness and effective signal responsiveness.

To bridge this gap, this study develops and characterizes a CNT-epoxy concrete, a hybrid repair material designed to achieve compressive sensing functionality and structural reinforcement simultaneously. The material combines CNTs with an epoxy matrix and coarse aggregates, forming a bulk composite suitable for crack region replacement. The effects of CNT concentration on conductivity, mechanical performance, and rheology were investigated in detail. Furthermore, its strain-sensing behavior under static and cyclic compression was analyzed to determine its viability as a localized SHM-enabled repair material for damaged concrete infrastructure.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

To develop a structurally applicable self-sensing repair material, a composite system was formulated using multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs), epoxy resin, and aggregates. The MWCNTs used in this study were MWCNT-210P (Kumho Petrochemical, Republic of Korea), synthesized by chemical vapor deposition. These nanotubes have diameters of approximately 10–15 nm and lengths of 10–20 μm , with a carbon purity exceeding 95 wt%. The epoxy matrix was based on a super-low viscosity bisphenol-A type resin (DH-150, Daehwa Precision, Republic of Korea), selected for its high fluidity (120 mPa·s), high compressive strength (76 MPa), and excellent bonding properties (adhesive strength: 9.1 MPa). Analytical-grade acetone (99.7%, Samchun Chemical, Republic of Korea) was used to facilitate the dispersion of CNTs in the epoxy matrix. Standard sand (KS L ISO 679) was used as the aggregate, due to its consistent particle size and compatibility with epoxy matrices. An 80:20 volumetric mixing ratio between aggregate and CNT-epoxy composite was adopted, based on prior optimization studies that achieved a balance between compressive performance, elasticity, and flowability. This configuration allows the material to mimic the load-bearing characteristics of typical crack repair regions in concrete structures.

2.2 Fabrication Process

The fabrication sequence of the CNT-epoxy concrete. The process was designed to achieve uniform CNT dispersion while maintaining the structural integrity of the composite during aggregate mixing and curing. First, CNTs were dispersed in approximately 50 mL of acetone together with the epoxy resin using an ultrasonicator (Q700, Qsonica, USA) at 90% amplitude in pulse mode (15 s on, 15 s off) for 40 minutes. This ultrasonic treatment was critical to overcome van der Waals attractions between CNTs, facilitating homogeneous dispersion. To prevent thermal degradation of the resin during sonication, the beaker was immersed in an ice bath. Following dispersion, the mixture was heated on a hot plate at 60 °C for 24 hours to evaporate the acetone. An epoxy hardener was then added in a 3:1 ratio (resin:hardener), and the mixture was further homogenized using a three-roll mill (TR50M, Trilos, USA) to remove remaining agglomerates and ensure uniform CNT distribution. This step was particularly important for consistent electrical conductivity and reproducible sensing behavior. The final CNT-epoxy composite was manually blended with aggregates and poured into cylindrical molds (40 mm diameter, 25 mm height). Curing was performed at room temperature for 48 hours. After demolding, both top and bottom surfaces were coated with high-purity silver ink to form low-resistance electrical contacts.

Figure 1: Fabrication process of CNT-epoxy concrete.

2.3 Characterization Methods

Electrical conductivity was measured using a two-probe setup. For samples with resistance above $10^6 \Omega$, a high-resistance meter (6517B, Keithley, USA) was used; for those below this threshold, a source meter (2450, Keithley, USA) was applied. The electrical conductivity σ (S/m) was calculated using

$$\sigma = L/RA \quad (1)$$

where R is the resistance, L is the electrode spacing, and A is the electrode cross-sectional area. Silver ink was applied to reduce contact resistance, and copper leads were attached during mechanical tests.

Mechanical and piezoresistive tests were conducted using a universal testing machine (Instron 8861, USA). Static compression tests were performed at a loading rate of 1.3 mm/min. Electrical resistance was recorded in real-time during mechanical loading using a multimeter (2700, Keithley, USA) connected to the copper-taped electrode surfaces. Rheological behavior of the CNT-epoxy composite was measured using a parallel-plate rheometer (MCR 302e, Anton Paar, Austria). A constant shear strain of 1.01% was applied across a frequency sweep from 0.05 to 450 rad/s to evaluate viscoelastic responses relevant to processability and field application.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Electrical Properties

The electrical conductivity of the CNT-epoxy composite exhibited a strong dependence on the CNT concentration. In specimens without CNTs or with less than 0.05 wt.% loading, the material behaved as an insulator, with conductivity below 10^{-8} S/m [3]. This is attributed to the isolated and randomly distributed CNTs, which were insufficient to form continuous pathways for electron transport. However, as the CNT concentration approached 0.10 wt.%, a dramatic increase in conductivity was observed. This behavior corresponds to the percolation threshold, where conductive clusters begin to connect and establish long-range networks through the matrix [4].

Between 0.10 wt.% and 0.50 wt.%, the conductivity rose by over three orders of magnitude, reaching values in the range of 10^{-5} to 10^{-3} S/m depending on sample geometry and aggregate presence. This exponential growth indicates efficient CNT network formation, enabling both direct conduction and electron tunneling. The results are consistent with previous findings in CNT/epoxy composites, where the percolation threshold is often reported between 0.05 and 0.3 wt.% depending on dispersion quality and processing method [5].

Beyond 0.50 wt.%, conductivity growth plateaued, suggesting saturation of the network. At these higher concentrations, additional CNTs are more likely to form redundant bundles or agglomerates rather than contributing to new connections [6]. This saturation effect limits further gains in sensing performance and suggests diminishing returns at higher loading levels.

Figure 2: Electrical conductivity of CNT-epoxy composites at different CNT concentrations.

3.2 Rheological Properties

The rheological characteristics of the CNT-epoxy composites were evaluated to understand how increasing CNT concentration affects processability. Table 1 presents the complex viscosity as a function of angular frequency for four CNT loadings: 0.00, 0.25, 0.50, and 2.50 wt.%.

The control sample with 0.00 wt.% CNT exhibited Newtonian-like flow behavior, maintaining a nearly constant viscosity of approximately 1 Pa·s across the entire frequency range. This low and stable viscosity is suitable for uniform mixing with aggregates and effective casting. Upon adding 0.25 wt.% CNT, a noticeable increase in viscosity was observed, particularly in the low-frequency range. The composite began to exhibit mild shear-thinning behavior, suggesting the onset of a weak particle–matrix interaction. Although the viscosity rose by nearly an order of magnitude, the material remained sufficiently flowable for practical mixing and casting processes. At 0.50 wt.%, the shear-thinning effect became more pronounced. The low-frequency viscosity further increased to above 10^4 Pa·s, indicating the development of a more interconnected CNT network within the epoxy. This enhanced viscoelastic response implies that the CNTs were forming physical linkages that resisted deformation under low shear conditions. A substantial rheological change was observed at 2.50 wt.%, where the composite reached a complex viscosity exceeding 10^6 Pa·s at low frequencies. The material became highly viscoelastic and showed significant resistance to flow. Such high viscosity can severely compromise workability, leading to poor dispersion of aggregates, increased air entrapment, and inhomogeneous distribution during casting. In practical applications, these issues could reduce both structural reliability and sensing stability.

The progressive increase in viscosity with CNT content is primarily driven by van der Waals forces between nanotubes, which promote physical entanglement and the formation of a pseudo-solid network. While beneficial for electrical conductivity, this network formation adversely affects flowability, especially in systems containing solid fillers such as sand [7].

Table 1: Complex viscosity of CNT-epoxy composites at different CNT concentrations.

CNT concentration (wt.%)	Complex viscosity (Pa·s)
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0.00	~1
0.25	~1.2 × 10 ³
0.50	~8 × 10 ³
2.50	~4 × 10 ⁵

3.3 Mechanical Behavior

The compressive performance of CNT-epoxy concrete was evaluated to investigate how varying CNT concentrations influence the mechanical response and to ensure that the sensing functionality does not compromise structural integrity. Figure 3 presents the compressive stress–strain curves for composites containing 0.00, 0.25, and 0.50 wt.% CNTs. The 2.50 wt.% formulation was excluded from mechanical testing due to workability issues during mixing and casting.

The control sample without CNTs exhibited brittle failure, with a peak strain of approximately 6.2% and a compressive strength of about 38 MPa. Incorporating 0.25 wt.% CNTs led to a strength increase of around 19%, reaching nearly 45 MPa, while the strain at failure more than doubled to 13.5%. This improvement is attributed to the reinforcing effect of CNTs, which can bridge microcracks, delay crack propagation, and enhance stress transfer between the matrix and the aggregates [8].

At 0.50 wt.%, the compressive strength was slightly lower than at 0.25 wt.% but still exceeded that of the control. The strain capacity remained comparable to the 0.25 wt.% sample, suggesting that the toughness improvements were retained. This result implies that moderate CNT loading can improve both strength and ductility without significantly affecting casting quality or material homogeneity.

These findings highlight the importance of identifying an optimal CNT range that provides both mechanical reinforcement and sensing capability. While low-to-moderate CNT contents enhance material performance, concentrations above 0.50 wt.% may lead to severe rheological limitations that hinder practical application. Therefore, a target range of 0.25–0.50 wt.% is recommended for CNT-epoxy concrete designed for use as a structural repair material with integrated self-sensing functionality.

Figure 3: Compressive stress–strain curves of CNT-epoxy concrete.

3.4 Electromechanical Response under Compressive Loading

Figure 4 presents the relative resistance change ($\Delta R/R_0$) of CNT-epoxy concrete specimens with 0.25 and 0.50 wt.% CNT content under uniaxial compression. As compressive stress increased, both samples exhibited a continuous decrease in electrical resistance, indicating the formation and densification of conductive paths within the matrix.

At the initial stage of loading, a steep decline in $\Delta R/R_0$ was observed, particularly for the 0.25 wt.% specimen. This behavior is attributed to the rapid reduction in tunneling distances between CNTs as the matrix is compressed, thereby enhancing conductive network density[9]. As the stress level increased further, the slope of the $\Delta R/R_0$ curve gradually decreased, reaching a near-plateau region. This transition suggests that the CNT network had reached a mechanically stable configuration, where additional compression induced relatively minor changes in resistance.

Compared to the 0.50 wt.% sample, the 0.25 wt.% specimen showed a greater initial sensitivity, reflected by a steeper slope in the low-stress regime. This indicates that the composite near the percolation threshold is more responsive to mechanical perturbations due to its loosely connected network[11], which is more susceptible to rearrangement under strain. On the other hand, the 0.50 wt.% composite exhibited a more moderate and stable resistance change[10], likely due to a denser and more saturated conductive network. These results confirm that CNT-epoxy concrete possesses piezoresistive properties suitable for self-sensing applications. In particular, composites near the percolation threshold (e.g., 0.25 wt.%) are more sensitive to compressive stress and thus may be more effective for detecting minor structural loads. However, higher CNT concentrations may offer better signal stability under sustained loading conditions.

Figure 4: Relative resistance change of CNT-epoxy concrete under compressive loading.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study investigated the electrical, rheological, mechanical, and electromechanical behavior of CNT-epoxy concrete for use as a self-sensing repair material. The results demonstrated that a CNT concentration between 0.25 and 0.50 wt.% offers the best balance between conductivity, processability, and mechanical performance.

Electrical conductivity increased sharply near 0.10 wt.%, indicating a clear percolation threshold. Rheological analysis showed that viscosity rose significantly with CNT content, especially above 0.50 wt.%, which negatively affected workability. Compressive tests revealed that 0.25 wt.% CNT

improved both strength and ductility, while higher concentrations showed diminishing returns. The electromechanical response confirmed the piezoresistive behavior of the composites, with 0.25 wt.% offering higher sensitivity and 0.50 wt.% showing more stable responses under compression.

Overall, CNT-epoxy concrete with 0.25–0.50 wt.% CNT is suitable for practical structural repair applications with built-in sensing capability. Further work is needed to evaluate long-term durability and field-scale implementation.

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